

Euphorbia mauritanica Yellow milk bush

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 1 m

Distribution:

This species is widely distributed across southern Africa, occurring in the Northern, Western, and Eastern Cape, Free State, KwaZulu-Natal, and Namibia. It is the most widely distributed South African shrubby euphorbia and is especially dominant in the Succulent Karoo, where it commonly occurs on valleys and hillsides.

Importance:

The yellow milk bush is toxic to livestock and sometimes confused with another succulent shrub used as forage, but it is valued as a drought-tolerant ornamental. In southern Africa, members of the Euphorbiaceae face increasing threats from illegal trade, highlighting the need for urgent conservation.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 199.73 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 24.18 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 6.08 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.8% [Single: 32.0%, Duplicated: 67.8%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 46 174.4 kilobases

Contig number: 1 074

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